
Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Accelerated Thermal Conductivity Testing of Insulation for QA/QC

The following Application Highlight addresses the thermal conductivity measurement of rockwool insulation using the Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) method.

Steady-state methods such as the Heat Flow Meter (HFM) and Guarded Hot Plate (GHP) are widely considered as the “golden standard” for thermal conductivity measurements of insulation materials. While highly accurate, a significant drawback to these methods is the long test times that are required for measurement. This is related to the fundamental way in which steady-state methods operate and the required stability criteria of the system (*further information can be found in ASTM C518/C177*). Stability time is ultimately subject to the materials’ thermal conductivity and overall thickness.

Figure 1. Left) Rockwool insulation sample. Right) C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument.

Transient-based methods of thermal analysis, such as C-Therm's Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS), have been shown to provide high quality measurements in a fraction of the time of more traditional steady-state options. Transient solutions also benefit in being more flexible on sample size requirements, compatible material type and overall valid testable conductivity range. The following data compares measurements on a rockwool sample using both MTPS and HFM at room temperature.

Figure 2. MTPS vs HFM test result (error bars represent $\pm 5\%$ accuracy).

Results from both methods are in excellent agreement (within 2.1%). The main difference in these measurements is related to the overall test time. HFM data above represents a single data point which was obtained after 6 hours of run time. MTPS results are the average of 3 measurements which took only 3 mins. With similar accuracy, the significantly faster MTPS method provides users the ability to rapidly test materials saving considerable instrument and operator time, especially important in high-throughput QA/QC applications.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com